

DIAGNOSTIC ROLE OF CYTOKINE PROFILE IN CHRONIC PYELONEPHRITIS IN CHILDREN.

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Currently, pyelonephritis, as a nonspecific microbial-inflammatory disease of the renal calyceal-pelvic system and tubulointerstitial kidney tissue, has a high prevalence among the pediatric population. Primarily, pyelonephritis, although less common than lower urinary tract infections, poses a serious threat to children's health and, in severe cases, can lead to kidney damage and the development of chronic kidney disease [3,6]. The high prevalence of severe complications of pyelonephritis, such as nephrosclerosis, kidney failure, and renal arterial hypertension, justifies the need for timely early diagnosis and prevention of this disease in children and adolescents. The outcome of chronic pyelonephritis (CP) depends on early diagnosis and timely initiation of therapy [2,5].

Despite the existence of numerous diagnostic methods for CP, new approaches are still being explored to assess the activity of inflammation and the persistence of clinical and laboratory remission. The study of immunopathological mechanisms in pediatric kidney pathology is highly relevant for analyzing the pathogenetic mechanisms of disease development [1]. Recent studies emphasize the investigation of local inflammatory mechanisms by examining interleukin levels in blood and urine. Interleukin-8 (IL-8) plays a dominant role in neutrophil activation and belongs to the group of pro-inflammatory cytokines [4,5].

The aim of this study was to analyze the cytokine profile in children with chronic pyelonephritis to assess the severity of the inflammatory process in renal tissue[6].

Materials and Methods

A clinical and laboratory examination was conducted on 35 children aged 1 to 15 years with chronic pyelonephritis (CP) during an exacerbation period, all of whom were receiving inpatient treatment. All patients underwent general clinical laboratory tests and specific blood analyses. The study material was peripheral venous blood. The control group consisted of 40 practically healthy children. IL-8 levels in the blood serum of children with CP were determined using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The diagnosis of chronic

pyelonephritis, as well as the severity of the disease and exacerbations in children, was established according to existing standards provided by the modern classification of clinical forms of the disease.

Results

The study results showed that during the exacerbation period of the disease, the clinical picture included extrarenal manifestations such as intoxication syndrome, abdominal pain syndrome, and lumbar pain. Children exhibited the Pasternacki symptom and dysuric disorders, including frequent urination. The urinary syndrome was characterized by isolated leukocyturia, often accompanied by hematuria and proteinuria, with all cases of leukocyturia having a neutrophilic nature.

The aim of our study was to assess the impact of chronic pyelonephritis on the synthesis of interleukin-8 in the blood of affected children. The examination was conducted during the exacerbation period, on the second day of hospital admission. A thorough collection of clinical and anamnestic data in the examined groups revealed that endogenous risk factors for chronic pyelonephritis (CP) included anemia, paratrophy, and food allergies. Analysis of the obstetric and somatic history of the mothers of the examined children showed that birth asphyxia and prematurity were among the risk factors for CP development in children. Among exogenous risk factors, frequent urinary tract infections were noted.

The study results of IL-8 levels in peripheral blood in children with CP demonstrated significant differences compared to the control group. The cytokine profile of IL-8, classified as a pro-inflammatory cytokine, was measured in all examined patients during the exacerbation of the primary disease. The results showed a significant increase in IL-8 levels in the peripheral blood of children with CP compared to the control group. The IL-8 level in children with CP was **78.32±12.11 pg/ml**, whereas in the control group, it was **11.32±0.72 pg/ml** ($p<0.001$).

According to the study of pathogenetic mechanisms, these results confirm the infectious nature of inflammation in CP in children. The elevated IL-8 levels in children with CP may be associated with more frequent inflammatory episodes throughout the year.

Conclusion

A comparative analysis of IL-8 levels and risk factors demonstrated a significant increase in IL-8 in CP compared to healthy children. The elevated IL-8 levels in children with CP may be associated with recurrent inflammatory

episodes, leading to frequent disease relapses. Increased IL-8 levels, combined with risk factors, serve as a diagnostic criterion for chronic pyelonephritis, and the most significant elevation of these indicators can be considered a prognostic marker for the development of the disease in children.

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